

REVIEW OF FOREIGN PRACTICE ON COMBATING HUMAN TRAFFICKING

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Annotation: Human trafficking is one of the most dangerous crimes that infringe on human rights and freedom. Unfortunately, this phenomenon continues to exist because it brings high criminal income. Combating human trafficking requires not only legislative measures, but also cooperation between countries and sectors, including governmental and non-governmental organizations, as well as the public. It is necessary to raise awareness of the problem and inform about this global phenomenon. This thesis analyzes the practice of foreign countries in combating human trafficking.

Keywords: *investigator / initiation of a criminal case / investigative action / source of information about the crime / investigative situation / operational investigative activities.*

Victims of trafficking today are people of different genders, ages and nationalities. A report published by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime in 2021 indicates that women remain the main victims of human trafficking. 50% of all victims were trafficked for the purpose of sexual exploitation, 38% of them were subjected to forced labour, and 6% participated in criminal activities¹. In 2020, the UN Secretary-General noted that more than 40 million people in the world are subjected to modern forms of slavery, of which 71% are girls and women.

Human trafficking is one of the most dangerous crimes that infringe on human rights and freedoms. Unfortunately, this phenomenon continues to exist, as it brings a high criminal income. The UN estimates that the annual revenue generated by human trafficking is \$ 150 billion². Criminal groups conduct illegal activities using new methods and methods of deception and coercion.

Given the fact that trafficking in persons is classified as an organized transnational crime, special attention should be paid to international cooperation, as well as to conducting full preliminary investigations in each criminal case.

¹ World Day against Trafficking in Persons. UN Information Center in Moscow // [Electronic resource]: UN Information Center in Moscow. – Режим доступа: <http://www.unic.ru/press/vsemirnyi-denborty-storgovlei-lyudmi>.

² UN Report: the pandemic has worsened the threat of human trafficking, especially for women and girls // UN News: official website-2023. - URL: <https://news.un.org/ru/story/2020/09/1387132>.

One of the most high-profile cases of newborn trafficking occurred in Colombia in the 1980s. Then a wide-ranging network of child abduction and trafficking was uncovered, involving several people, including medical personnel, deceived mothers and gangs of criminals. As a result of the operation, dozens of people were arrested and convicted, and many of the abducted children were returned to their parents.

In recent years, trafficking in newborns has become more organized, and criminals are using more and more new methods to stay out of the sight of law enforcement agencies. However, many countries have adopted laws to combat these crimes. For example, in Sweden, medical personnel are required to report a discrepancy between the newborn and the mother or father, and an infanticide notification is introduced at the official level infanticide.

Globalization and digitalization create a breeding ground for the formation of criminal groups for human trafficking, providing super-profits at lower financial and physical costs. Modern slave traders use digital technology to recruit, control, and exploit their victims. They use the Internet, especially the Darknet phenomenon, to hide materials related to their criminal activities and the real identities of criminals. Illegal proceeds from this lucrative business are realized through cryptocurrencies, making it easier to obtain, hide, and move large amounts of money. Today, the Internet provides easy access to a much larger group of potential victims, as it allows you to level out traditional physical and geographical restrictions.³

In the United States, public organizations occupy an important place in the hierarchy of social partners of the state in the fight against human trafficking. They have a long history, accumulated experience and receive significant financial support from the state. One of the most well-known organizations is Polaris (Polaris Anti-Trafficking Project), which for many years has been conducting research and supervising the National Hotline for Victims of Human Trafficking on behalf of the government. Polaris has the largest database on human trafficking in the United States, which is used to analyze the situation and identify trends, develop long-term programs and strategic solutions.⁴

For example, annual statistics generated from calls to the hotline in 2019 revealed 22,326 victims of human trafficking, 11,500 cases, 4,384 criminals, and 1,912 businesses that are suspected of using forced or trafficked labour.

³ Oskina E. A. Political and legal features of combating human trafficking in the context of political polarization and hybridization. Analysis and forecast. IMEMO RAS Journal, 2022, no. 1. pp.100-117.

⁴ <https://polarisproject.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/Typology-of-Modern-Slavery-Summary.pdf>

In addition, Polaris participates in joint projects with the International Organization for Migration to create a global resource on human trafficking and constantly updates the list of public organizations working in this area from around the world.

In recent years, trafficking in newborns has become more organized, and criminals are using more and more new methods to stay out of the sight of law enforcement agencies. However, many countries have adopted laws to combat these crimes. Identification of accomplices in crimes related to those accused of committing these crimes (in a chain) abroad, in delivering them to the Republic of Uzbekistan, and in cases of refusal, in procedural detention and initiation of criminal cases against them, taking into account that some of the crimes are committed on the territory of a foreign state, it is necessary to send instructions to the relevant law enforcement agencies state authorities, on conducting preliminary investigative actions with the provision of copies of the procedural materials to the investigative bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (when a foreign national is detained and charged)

Article 592 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan – defines the procedure for sending a request for proceeding in a foreign country.

Thus, if it is necessary to perform these procedural actions on the territory of a foreign state-by courts, prosecutor's offices, investigative bodies, a request is sent to perform these actions by the competent authorities of a foreign state in accordance with international treaties with the Republic of Uzbekistan or on the basis of the principle of reciprocity.

The principle of reciprocity is confirmed by written obligations of the Supreme Court, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the State Security Service and the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan to provide legal assistance to the competent body of a foreign State in performing certain procedural actions on the territory of a foreign State within the framework of cooperation on the principle of reciprocity.

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